

ASSESSING THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPLICATIONS OF PHARMACEUTICAL WASTE ON SOIL QUALITY IN LAGOS, NIGERIA: A CASE FOR IMPLEMENTING TAKE-BACK PROGRAMS

*Iretiolu C. Lasore^{1,2}; Labunmi Lajide⁴; Zacchaeus S. Ololade^{3,4}; Joshua O. Babayemi⁵

¹Department of Chemical Sciences, Anchor University, Lagos, Nigeria

²Center for Global Health, Anchor University, Lagos

³Department of Pharmaceutical and Medicinal Chemistry, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Nigeria

⁴Department of Chemistry, Medicinal and Organic Chemistry Unit, University of Medical Sciences,
Ondo, Nigeria

⁵Department of Biosciences and Biotechnology, University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Nigeria

bmlajide@unimed.edu.ng⁴, sololade@unimed.edu.ng^{3,4}, jbabayemi@unimed.edu.ng⁵,

clasore@aui.edu.ng^{1,2}

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18050538>

Abstract

This study examined pharmaceutical residues in soil from waste storage sites in Lagos, Nigeria, revealing environmental and public health risks due to poor waste management. 16 soil samples were analyzed for Ciprofloxacin, Paracetamol, and Bromazepam, with concentrations ranging from 0.29 to 269.66 mg/kg across five samples (S001, S015, S012, Xp1, S008). Paracetamol showed the highest levels (269.66 mg/kg in S008), followed by Bromazepam (153.60 mg/kg in S008) and Ciprofloxacin (25.04 mg/kg in S008). Sample Xp1, distant from waste sites, had lower concentrations, indicating contamination hotspots. These levels exceed typical soil concentrations (0.01–10 mg/kg), suggesting inadequate disposal practices. Ciprofloxacin's presence raises concerns, as sublethal levels may promote resistance in soil microbes. Paracetamol may disrupt microbial activity and nutrient cycling, while Bromazepam could affect soil invertebrates. Exceeding WHO limits, these findings highlight the need for sustainable pharmaceutical waste management, including Pharmacy-led Take-back programs, to align with SDGs 3, 6, and 12.

Keywords: Waste, Pharmaceutical, Soil, Take-Back